

Use-Cases POSTDATA Domain Model

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Title: Use-Cases POSTDATA Domain Model

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Abstract

This document is framed in the work of defining a domain model (or data model) for the European Poetry (EP). This work includes the study of the data structures of several databases of repertoires elected as representatives of the EP. Some of these repertoires did not make available its data structure so the POSTDATA team analysed the correspondent graphical user interface (GUI) on the Web of Documents to understand its informational needs. The work also includes the study of a survey to final users of the data, and the construction of use-cases that use real data from resources available in five different repositories. See <https://goo.gl/00mqhI> for more details about the repositories that are used to define the Domain Model. This document presents the use-cases made with resources from six different projects.

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Preliminary remarks

In order to create the domain model for the European poetry, the POSTDATA team selected representatives of the European Poetry for which they have conducted:

- Analysis of their database structure (when available)
- Analysis of the informational needs of their graphical user interfaces (GUI)
- Analysis of a survey to users of these repertoires
- Elaboration of use-cases

This document presents the results of the last item of the list. To elaborate these use-cases, resources for each database were selected at random. In the case of the project *Eesti regilaulude andmebaas* (Chapter ??), four resources were chosen as a result of carrying-out different searches changing the criteria.

The contents of the use-cases are organised in tables. There is a table for each class of the POSTDATA data model present in that particular use-case. Each table presents the label for every instance of that class, the POSTDATA properties for which information is given, and finally, the range of said property.

In every case, the authors only included the information that was made explicit in the database. No inferences were made in an attempt to fill in additional fields.

Chapter 1

Bardic Poetry Database

Resource: URL

Creator: Helena Bermúdez Sabel

Table 1.1: Opus

Instance	Properties	Range
Opus1	title	Mo-chion dot bhronnadh, a Bhriain
	date	17th early
	function	Thanks mp
	theme	Feart feile, poetic miracle
	theme	the reading and writing of poetry
	theme	Historical comparisons
	comesFrom	Place1
	hasCreator	Creator1
	hasRole	Role1
	isRealisedThrough	Redaction1

Table 1.2: Creator

Instance	Properties	Range
Creator1	isA	Person1

Table 1.3: Redaction

Instance	Properties	Range
Redaction1	incipit	Mo-chion dot bhronnadh, a Bhriain
	additionalFile	https://bardic.celt.dias.ie/pdf/POEM1400.pdf
	considers	Witness1
	considers	Witness2
	considers	Witness3
	hasItem	Paratext1
	hasFirstStanza	Stanza1
	retrievesText	Location1
	isAnalysedThrough	WorkPattern1
	isAnalysedThrough	StanzaPattern1

Table 1.4: Stanza

Instance	Properties	Range
Stanza1	stanzaNumber	1
	hasFirstLine	Line1
	nextStanza	Stanza2
Stanza2	stanzaNumber	2
	hasFirstLine	Line5
	nextStanza	Stanza3
Stanza3	stanzaNumber	3
	hasFirstLine	Line9
	nextStanza	Stanza4
Stanza4	stanzaNumber	4
	hasFirstLine	Line13
	nextStanza	Stanza5
Stanza5	stanzaNumber	5
	hasFirstLine	Line17
	nextStanza	Stanza6
Stanza6	stanzaNumber	6
	hasFirstLine	Line21
	nextStanza	Stanza7
Stanza7	stanzaNumber	7
	hasFirstLine	Line25
	nextStanza	Stanza8
Stanza8	stanzaNumber	8
	hasFirstLine	Line29
	nextStanza	Stanza9
Stanza9	stanzaNumber	9
	hasFirstLine	Line33
	nextStanza	Stanza10
Stanza10	stanzaNumber	10
	hasFirstLine	Line37
	nextStanza	Stanza11
Stanza11	stanzaNumber	11
	hasFirstLine	Line41
	nextStanza	Stanza12
Stanza12	stanzaNumber	12
	hasFirstLine	Line45
	nextStanza	Stanza13
Stanza13	stanzaNumber	13
	hasFirstLine	Line49

Table 1.5: Line

Instance	Properties	Range
Line1	content	Mo chion dot bhronnadh, a Bhriain,
	nextLine	Line2
Line2	content	a mhic na flatha a finnChliaigh,
	nextLine	Line3
Line3	content	a aistrigh an toirbheirt truin,
	nextLine	Line4
Line4	content	h'aisgidh badh oirdheirc aguinn.

Continued on next page

Table 1.5 – continued from previous page

Instance	Properties	Range
Line5	content	Ní chuala go bhfuair ollamh
	nextLine	Line6
Line6	content	meadh don aisgidh fhuaramar;
	nextLine	Line7
Line7	content	dot ghruaidh ttaidhleach téid a mheas
	nextLine	Line8
Line8	content	tar mhéid ainbhreath na n-éigeas.
Line9	content	Cearc Bhoirche fhréimhe Rosa,
	nextLine	Line10
Line10	content	fhuair clú d'fhine Fhearghosa,
	nextLine	Line11
Line11	content	ger chúis iomráidh a hainm sin,
	nextLine	Line12
Line12	content	ní gairm ionráidh mar aisgidh.
Line13	content	Ó Mhaoil Sheachluinn eacht oile
	nextLine	Line14
Line14	content	d'ardollamh fhóid Ughoine,
	nextLine	Line15
Line15	content	nírbh iongnadh, tarla ar a thoil,
	nextLine	Line16
Line16	content	fionnbhruigh Banbha re bliadhoin.
Line17	content	Nír chosmhail a chur a suim
	nextLine	Line18
Line18	content	síneadh cinn do Choin Chuluinn,
	nextLine	Line19
Line19	content	d'fhior tuaighe táinic tar sál,
	nextLine	Line20
Line20	content	ó ráinic uaidhe iomshlán.
Line21	content	Eochaidh eachtach na n-arm nglan,
	nextLine	Line22
Line22	content	ní thug acht éanshúil d'ollamh,
	nextLine	Line23
Line23	content	giodh toirbheartus do thuair teann,
	nextLine	Line24
Line24	content	le bhfuair oirdhearcus Éireann.
Line25	content	Do dhearlaic sibhsi, asé a shuim,
	nextLine	Line26
Line26	content	tré bheith 'na n-amhghar oruinn,
	nextLine	Line27
Line27	content	do dhá ghoirdhearc dhamhsa am dhall,
	nextLine	Line28
Line28	content	almsa bhus oirdhearc agam.
Line29	content	Do-bhéaradh, a bharr na mionn,
	nextLine	Line30
Line30	content	dámadh leis aoibhnios Éirionn
	nextLine	Line31
Line31	content	ar son a radhairc, rún grinn,
	nextLine	Line32
Line32	content	dhúnn, 's a thabhairt fá thuairim.
Line33	content	Gi-bé do bhronn a dhá rosg,
	nextLine	Line34
Line34	content	fá chrodh ní cóir a theagosg,
	nextLine	Line35
Line35	content	barr gleannach dá ttarla ar ttol,
	nextLine	Line36
Line36	content	eallach Banbha do bhronnfadh.

Continued on next page

Table 1.5 – continued from previous page

Instance	Properties	Range
Line37	content	A ttugsat cách, beag a bhrígh,
	nextLine	Line38
Line38	content	d’Aithirne is d’Eochaidh Eígsín,
	nextLine	Line39
Line39	content	ar mheas lóigh na ngormrosg nglan
	nextLine	Line40
Line40	content	an dornasg óir níorbh iongnadh.
Line41	content	Ní thuigim nach feart féile
	nextLine	Line42
Line42	content	fuarus uait gan aimhréidhe,
	nextLine	Line43
Line43	content	do radharc, a thaobh mar thuinn,
	nextLine	Line44
Line44	content	’s an t-amharc mar aon aguinn.
Line45	content	Gá ttám ris, ní rádh bréige,
	nextLine	Line46
Line46	content	go bráth, a mhic Mairgréige,
	nextLine	Line47
Line47	content	biad mar mhalairt, más lór lat,
	nextLine	Line48
Line48	content	do lógh bhur n-amhairc agat.
Line49	content	Go n-íoca Dia red dhreich ndil
	nextLine	Line50
Line50	content	bronnadh le léighim litir
	nextLine	Line51
Line51	content	is ré sgríobhuim seal mar so
	nextLine	Line52
Line52	content	is mo chean d’fhíorroinn m’anno.

Table 1.6: Location

Instance	Properties	Range
Location1	workNumber	poem 14
	refersAsPart	BibliographicSource1

Table 1.7: BibliographicSource

Instance	Properties	Range
BibliographicSource1	title	Irish Bardic Poetry
	date	1970
	pubPlace	Dublin
	hasEditor	Person2

Table 1.8: Paratext

Instance	Properties	Range
Paratext1	typeOfParatext	Apologue
	class	Cearc Boirche
	class	Fled Bricrenn
	class	Maoileachlainn gives kgshp to MacCoise

Table 1.9: Person

Instance	Properties	Range
Person1	surname	O Corcraín
	forename	Brian
	altName	BOCD
Person2	surname	Bergin
	forename	Osborn
Person3	surname	MagUídhir
	forename	Brian
	deathDate	1632

Table 1.10: Role

Instance	Properties	Range
Role1	function	sponsor
	certainty	3
	isAssignedTo	Person3

Table 1.11: Place

Instance	Properties	Range
Place1	region	Ulster

Table 1.12: PrimarySource

Instance	Properties	Range
PrimarySource1	title	RIA 625 (3/C/12) O'Curry trscr. BOCD
PrimarySource2	title	Book of O'Conor Don
	date	c. 1631
PrimarySource3	title	transl. Bergin IBP no. 14
	isPrint	true

Table 1.13: Witness

Instance	Properties	Range
Witness1	isPart	PrimarySource1
Witness2	isPart	PrimarySource2
Witness3	isPart	PrimarySource3

Table 1.14: WorkPattern

Instance	Properties	Range
WorkPattern1	numberOfStanzas	13
	typeOfRhymeMatching	deibhidhe
	notes	length: short

Table 1.15: StanzaPattern

Instance	Properties	Range
StanzaPattern1	metricalType	qq

Chapter 2

Cantigas de Santa Maria for Singers

Resource: URL

Creators: Patrícia Garrido Teixeira & Mariana Curado Malta

Editor: Mariana Curado Malta

Notes: Since the images of the musical transcriptions are created on-the-fly, we have used the link provided for the images even if they were not URL. We know it is not a URL but the idea was to show that the model works.

Table 2.1: Opus

Instance	Properties	Range
Opus1	title	Mais nos faz Santa Maria
	isRealisedThrough	Redaction1

Table 2.2: Redaction

Instance	Properties	Range
Redaction1	originalTitle	Mais nos faz Santa Maria
	hasFirstStanza	StanzaRefrain
	isAnalysedThrough	WorkPattern1
	isUsedIn	Performance1
	isUsedIn	Performance2
	isUsedIn	Performance3
	isUsedIn	Performance4
	isUsedIn	Performance5
	hasItem	Paratext1
	considers	Witness1
	considers	Witness2
	considers	Witness3
	isReferencedIn	Location1
	retrievesText	Location2

Table 2.3: Stanza

Instance	Properties	Range
StanzaRefrain	stanzaNumber	1
	nextStanza	Stanza1
	isAnalysedThrough	SP1
	hasFirstLine	Line1
Stanza1	stanzaNumber	2
	isRefrainOmitted	1
	nextStanza	Stanza2
	hasFirstLine	Line5
Stanza2	stanzaNumber	3
	isRefrainOmitted	1
	nextStanza	Stanza3
	hasFirstLine	Line13
Stanza3	stanzaNumber	4
	isRefrainOmitted	1
	nextStanza	Stanza4
	hasFirstLine	Line21
Stanza4	stanzaNumber	5
	isRefrainOmitted	1
	nextStanza	Stanza5
	hasFirstLine	Line29
Stanza5	stanzaNumber	6
	isRefrainOmitted	1
	hasFirstLine	Line37

Table 2.4: Line

Instance	Properties	Range
LineRefrain1	content	Mais nos faz Santa María...
	isRefrain	yes
Line1	lineNumber	1
	content	Mais nos faz Santa María
	isRefrain	yes
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern1
	presents	Rhyme1
	nextLine	Line2
Line2	lineNumber	2
	content	a séu Fillo perdõar,
	isRefrain	yes
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern2
	presents	Rhyme2
	nextLine	Line3
Line3	lineNumber	3
	content	que nós per nóssa folía
	isRefrain	yes
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern3
	presents	Rhyme1
	nextLine	Line4
Line4	lineNumber	4
	content	ll' imos falir e errar.
	isRefrain	yes
	presents	Rhyme2
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern4

Continued on next page

Table 2.4 – continued from previous page

Instance	Properties	Range
Line5	lineNumber	5
	content	Por ela nos perdōou
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern5
	presents	Rhyme3
	nextLine	Line6
Line6	lineNumber	6
	content	Déus o pecado d' Adán
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern6
	presents	Rhyme8
	nextLine	Line7
Line7	lineNumber	7
	content	da maçãa que gostou,
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern7
	presents	Rhyme3
	nextLine	Line8
Line8	lineNumber	8
	content	per que sofreu muit' afán
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern8
	presents	Rhyme8
	nextLine	Line9
Line9	lineNumber	9
	content	e no inférno entrou;
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern9
	presents	Rhyme3
	nextLine	Line10
Line10	lineNumber	10
	content	mais a do mui bon talán
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern10
	presents	Rhyme8
	nextLine	Line11
Line11	lineNumber	11
	content	tant' a séu Fillo rogou,
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern11
	presents	Rhyme3
	nextLine	Line12
Line12	lineNumber	12
	content	que o foi end' el sacar.
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern12
	presents	Rhyme2
	nextLine	LineRefrain1
Line13	lineNumber	13
	content	Pois ar fez perdón aver
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern13
	presents	Rhyme4
	nextLine	Line14
Line14	lineNumber	14
	content	a Teófilo, un séu
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern14
	presents	Rhyme9
	nextLine	Line15
Line15	lineNumber	15
	content	sérvo, que fora fazer
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern15
	presents	Rhyme4
	nextLine	Line16

Continued on next page

Table 2.4 – continued from previous page

Instance	Properties	Range
Line16	lineNumber	16
	content	per consello dun judéu
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern16
	presents	Rhyme9
	nextLine	Line17
Line17	lineNumber	17
	content	carta por gâar poder
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern17
	presents	Rhyme4
	nextLine	Line18
Line18	lineNumber	18
	content	cono démo, e lla déu;
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern18
	presents	Rhyme9
	nextLine	Line19
Line19	lineNumber	19
	content	e fez-ll' en Déus descreer,
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern19
	presents	Rhyme4
	nextLine	Line20
Line20	lineNumber	20
	content	des i a ela negar.
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern20
	presents	Rhyme2
	nextLine	LineRefrain1
Line21	lineNumber	21
	content	Pois Teófilo assí
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern21
	presents	Rhyme5
	nextLine	Line22
Line22	lineNumber	22
	content	fez aquesta traïçôn,
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern22
	presents	Rhyme10
	nextLine	Line23
Line23	lineNumber	22
	content	per quant' end' éu aprendí,
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern23
	presents	Rhyme5
	nextLine	Line24
Line24	lineNumber	24
	content	foi do démo gran sazôn;
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern24
	presents	Rhyme10
	nextLine	Line25
Line25	lineNumber	25
	content	mais depois, segund' oí,
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern25
	presents	Rhyme5
	nextLine	Line26
Line26	lineNumber	26
	content	repentiu-s' e foi perdôn
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern26
	presents	Rhyme10
	nextLine	Line27

Continued on next page

Table 2.4 – continued from previous page

Instance	Properties	Range
Line27	lineNumber	27
	content	pedir lógo, ben alí
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern27
	presents	Rhyme5
	nextLine	Line28
Line28	lineNumber	28
	content	u pecador sól achar.
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern28
	presents	Rhyme2
	nextLine	Line29
Line29	lineNumber	29
	content	Chorando dos ollos séus
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern29
	presents	Rhyme6
	nextLine	Line30
Line30	lineNumber	30
	content	muito, foi perdôn pedir,
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern30
	presents	Rhyme11
	nextLine	Line31
Line31	lineNumber	31
	content	u viu da Madre de Déus
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern31
	presents	Rhyme6
	nextLine	Line32
Line32	lineNumber	32
	content	a omagen; sen falir
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern32
	presents	Rhyme11
	nextLine	Line33
Line33	lineNumber	33
	content	lle diss’: “Os pecados méus
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern33
	presents	Rhyme6
	nextLine	Line34
Line34	lineNumber	34
	content	son tan muitos, sen mentir,
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern34
	presents	Rhyme11
	nextLine	Line35
Line35	lineNumber	35
	content	que, se non per rógos téus,
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern35
	presents	Rhyme6
	nextLine	Line36
Line36	lineNumber	36
	content	non póss’ éu perdôn gãar.”
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern36
	presents	Rhyme2
	nextLine	LineRefrain1
Line37	lineNumber	37
	content	Teófilo dessa vez
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern37
	presents	Rhyme7
	nextLine	Line38

Continued on next page

Table 2.4 – continued from previous page

Instance	Properties	Range
Line38	lineNumber	38
	content	chorou tant' e non fez al,
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern38
	presents	Rhyme12
	nextLine	Line39
Line39	lineNumber	39
	content	trões u a que de prez
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern39
	presents	Rhyme7
	nextLine	Line40
Line40	lineNumber	40
	content	todas outras donas val,
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern40
	presents	Rhyme12
	nextLine	Line41
Line41	lineNumber	41
	content	ao démo mais ca pez
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern41
	presents	Rhyme7
	nextLine	Line42
Line42	lineNumber	42
	content	negro do fógu' infernal
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern42
	presents	Rhyme12
	nextLine	Line43
Line43	lineNumber	43
	content	a carta trager-lle fez,
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern43
	presents	Rhyme7
	nextLine	Line44
Line44	lineNumber	44
	content	e déu-lla ant' o altar.
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern44
	presents	Rhyme2
	nextLine	LineRefrain1

Table 2.5: LinePattern

Instance	Properties	Range
LinePattern1	syllabicMetricalScheme	7'
	phoneticTranscription	mais nos fadsanta mari.a
	scannedLine	Mais nos faz San•ta Ma•rí•a
LinePattern2	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	a seufilo perdoḡar
	scannedLine	a séu Fi•llo per•dõ•ar,
LinePattern3	syllabicMetricalScheme	7'
	phoneticTranscription	ke nōs per nōsa foli.a
	scannedLine	que nōs per nō•ssa fo•lí•a
LinePattern4	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	limos falir e errar
	scannedLine	ll' i•mos fa•lir e e•rrar.
LinePattern5	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	por ela nos perdoḡou
	scannedLine	Por e•la nos per•dõ•ou

Continued on next page

Table 2.5 – continued from previous page

Instance	Properties	Range
LinePattern6	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	d̥ɛʊs o pekado dadaj
	scannedLine	D̥ɛʊs o pe•ca•do d' A•dán
LinePattern7	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	da maaja ke gostou
	scannedLine	da ma•çã•a que gos•tou,
LinePattern8	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	per ke sofreumuitafaj
	scannedLine	per que so•freu mui•t' a•fán
LinePattern9	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	e no iŋferno entrou
	scannedLine	e no in•fér•no en•trou;
LinePattern10	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	mais a do muiβon talaɲ
	scannedLine	mais a do mui bon ta•lán
LinePattern11	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	tanta seufilo rrogou
	scannedLine	tan•t' a séu Fi•llo ro•gou,
LinePattern12	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	ke o fojendel sakar
	scannedLine	que o foi en•d' el sa•car.
LinePattern13	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	pois ar fedzperdoɲ aβer
	scannedLine	Pois ar fez per•dón a•ver
LinePattern14	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	a te.ɔfilo uɲ seɯ
	scannedLine	a Te•ó•fi•lo, un séu
LinePattern15	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	serβo ke fora fadzer
	scannedLine	sér•vo, que fo•ra fa•zer
LinePattern16	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	per konseɮo duɲ ɟudeɯ
	scannedLine	per con•sse•llo dun ju•déu
LinePattern17	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	karta por gaɲar poder
	scannedLine	car•ta por gã•ar po•der
LinePattern18	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	kono demo e la deɯ
	scannedLine	co•no dé•mo, e lla déu;
LinePattern19	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	e fedzɮeɲ d̥ɛʊs deskre.er
	scannedLine	e fez-ll' en D̥ɛʊs des•cre•er,
LinePattern20	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	des i a ela negar
	scannedLine	des i a e•la ne•gar.
LinePattern21	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	pois te.ɔfilo asi
	scannedLine	Pois Te•ó•fi•lo a•ssí
LinePattern22	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	fedzakesta tra.ioɲ
	scannedLine	fez a•ques•ta tra•i•çón,
LinePattern23	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	per kuantend̥ɛɯaprendi
	scannedLine	per quan•t' en•d' éu a•pren•dí,
LinePattern24	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	fojdo demo graɲ sadɔɲ
	scannedLine	foi do dé•mo gran sa•zón;

Continued on next page

Table 2.5 – continued from previous page

Instance	Properties	Range
LinePattern25	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	mais depois segundo.i
	scannedLine	mais de•pois, se•gun•d’ o•óí,
LinePattern26	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	rrepentiuse foiperdoŋ
	scannedLine	re•pen•tiu-s’ e foi per•dôn
LinePattern27	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	pedir lōgo beŋ ali
	scannedLine	pe•dir lō•go, ben a•lí
LinePattern28	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	u pekadōr sōl aar
	scannedLine	u pe•ca•dor sōl a•char.
LinePattern29	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	orando dos olos sēus
	scannedLine	Cho•ran•do dos o•llos séus
LinePattern30	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	muito foiperdoŋ pedir
	scannedLine	mui•to, foi per•dôn pe•dir,
LinePattern31	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	u βiŋda madre de deŋs
	scannedLine	u viu da Ma•dre de Déus
LinePattern32	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	a omaŋeŋ seŋ falir
	scannedLine	a o•ma•gen; sen fa•lir
LinePattern33	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	le disos pekados meŋs
	scannedLine	lle di•ss’: “Os pe•ca•dos méus
LinePattern34	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	soŋ taŋ muitos seŋ mentir
	scannedLine	son tan mui•tos, sen men•tir,
LinePattern35	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	ke se noŋ per rroŋos teŋs
	scannedLine	que, se non per ró•gos téus,
LinePattern36	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	noŋ pōseŋperdoŋ gaŋar
	scannedLine	non pó•ss’ éu per•dôn gã•ar.”
LinePattern37	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	te.ɔfilo desa βeð
	scannedLine	Te•ó•fi•lo de•ssa vez
LinePattern38	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	oroŋtante noŋ feðal
	scannedLine	cho•rou tan•t’ e non fez al,
LinePattern39	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	troŋes u a ke de preð
	scannedLine	trõ•es u a que de prez
LinePattern40	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	todas outras donas ßal
	scannedLine	to•das ou•tras do•nas val,
LinePattern41	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	a.o demo mais ka peð
	scannedLine	a•o dé•mo mais ca pez
LinePattern42	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	scannedLine	ne•gro do fó•gu’ in•fer•nal
	phoneticTranscription	negro do fōgijfernal
LinePattern43	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	a karta traðŋer le feð
	scannedLine	a car•ta tra•ger-lle fez,

Continued on next page

Table 2.5 – continued from previous page

Instance	Properties	Range
LinePattern44	syllabicMetricalScheme	7
	phoneticTranscription	e deυλα anto altar
	scannedLine	e déu-lla an●t' o al●tar.

Table 2.6: Rhyme

Instance	Properties	Range
Rhyme1	label	A
	ending	i.a
Rhyme2	label	B
	ending	aR
Rhyme3	label	c
	ending	ou
Rhyme4	label	c
	ending	eR
Rhyme5	label	c
	ending	i
Rhyme6	label	c
	ending	Eus
Rhyme7	label	c
	ending	edz
Rhyme8	label	d
	ending	aN
Rhyme9	label	d
	ending	Eu
Rhyme10	label	d
	ending	oN
Rhyme11	label	d
	ending	iR
Rhyme12	label	d
	ending	al

Table 2.7: Paratext

Instance	Properties	Range
Paratext1	editedContent	Esta é como Santa María fez cobrar a Teófilo a carta que fezéra cono démo, u se tornou séu vassalo.

Table 2.8: Creator

Instance	Properties	Range
Creator1	isA	Person1

Table 2.9: Person

Instance	Properties	Range
Person1	name	Walater
	surname	Mettman

Table 2.10: Performance

Instance	Properties	Range
Performance1	tempo	Very Slow
	time	9:11
	syllablesPerMinute	50
Performance2	tempo	Slow
	time	4:35
	syllablesPerMinute	100
Performance3	tempo	Medium
	time	3:04
	syllablesPerMinute	150
Performance4	tempo	Fast
	time	2:17
	syllablesPerMinute	200
Performance5	tempo	Very Fast
	time	1:50
	syllablesPerMinute	250

Table 2.11: Witness

Instance	Properties	Range
Witness1	isReproducedIn	Facsimile1
	isPart	PrimarySource1
	hasMusicalNotation	MusicalNotation1
	hasMusicalNotation	MusicalNotation6
	hasMusicalNotation	MusicalNotation11
Witness2	isPart	PrimarySource2
Witness3	isReproducedIn	Facsimile2
	isPart	PrimarySource3

Table 2.12: Facsimile

Instance	Properties	Range
Facsimile1	url	http://www.pbm.com/~lindahl/cantigas/facsimiles/E/057small.html
Facsimile2	url	http://www.pbm.com/~lindahl/cantigas/facsimiles/To/bob003small.gif
	nextPage	Facsimile3
Facsimile3	url	http://www.pbm.com/~lindahl/cantigas/facsimiles/To/bob004small.gif

Table 2.13: PrimarySource

Instance	Properties	Range
PrimarySource1	siglum	E
	title	codice princeps
	altTitle	código de los músicos
	notes	The Escorial "codice princeps" (principal codex, signature j.b.2), held in the Real Biblioteca de San Lorenzo de El Escorial outside Madrid. Also known in Spanish as the código de los músicos—the musicians' codex—due to the well-known and oft-reproduced miniatures of performers and their instruments that appear before each of the Cantigas de Loo. This is by far the largest of the manuscripts, though modest in decoration compared to [T] and [F]. It contains the prologues and 406 of the cantigas, nine of which are repeated with mostly minor variations, and provides the basis for Mettmann's numbering scheme, which I use on this website.
PrimarySource2	siglum	T
	title	codice rico
	notes	the Escorial "codice rico" (rich codex), also in the El Escorial library, known as [T] from its manuscript signature T.j.1. Contains the prologues and 195 of the cantigas (originally 203, but eight are missing due to the loss of folios), roughly corresponding to the first half of [E].
PrimarySource3	siglum	To
	title	Toledo
	notes	the "Toledo" codex, now in the National Library of Madrid. It includes 129 cantigas, which are apparently amongst the oldest in terms of authorship. Mettmann considered the manuscript itself to be the youngest copy of the four, possibly from the start of the 14th century. Ferreira, on the other hand, considers it to be 'the oldest surviving source' from no later than 1280.

Table 2.14: MusicalNotation

Instance	Properties	Range
MusicalNotation1	typeOfMusicalNotation	Annotated transcription (diplomatic transcription)
	editionNotes	E1:The word nos is repeated on this stave in the manuscript, but is not assigned another note or ligature. E2:See E4. E3:This is a custos indicating the pitch of the note after the page break: these are commonplace in [To] but as far as I am aware this is the only one in [E]. By the way, all the custodes (pl.) in [To] have their stems down, so that's how they are rendered here, even though this one has its stem up in [E]. E4:Compare this odd-looking ligature (for one syllable) with the pair of separate notes at E2 in the refrain. E5:This line appears very faint in the manuscript facsimile. E6:The word a is repeated at the start of this stave, but is not assigned a note or ligature.
	imageOftranscription	blob:null/3db0b7bc-b426-4d5e-8d81-61324c6bb7c0
	nextTranscription	MusicalNotation2

Continued on next page

Table 2.14 – continued from previous page

Instance	Properties	Range
MusicalNotation2	imageOftranscription	blob:null/789e9ed8-0093-4db3-9436-8c6cfaf432ff
	nextTranscription	MusicalNotation3
MusicalNotation3	imageOftranscription	blob:null/12de2795-56cf-41bd-8b48-e5b2485bc3b7
	nextTranscription	MusicalNotation4
MusicalNotation4	imageOftranscription	blob:null/2a2c7ecb-c286-45dc-8288-8037726b7524
	nextTranscription	MusicalNotation5
MusicalNotation5	imageOftranscription	blob:null/67213e2c-5c86-4c4d-a709-0464ef0694bf
MusicalNotation6	typeOfMusicalNotation	Squase notation
	imageOftranscription	blob:null/78c8be00-5ea7-48a7-9f4d-5af081abc296
	nextTranscription	MusicalNotation7
MusicalNotation7	imageOftranscription	blob:null/3e717039-bad6-4818-b6e0-88908b30ab99
	nextTranscription	MusicalNotation8
MusicalNotation8	imageOftranscription	blob:null/a1e15e10-45aa-470c-b228-e6978233d697
	nextTranscription	MusicalNotation9
MusicalNotation9	imageOftranscription	blob:null/7d092dcc-6f42-47f0-bed8-247ca5280772
	nextTranscription	MusicalNotation10
MusicalNotation10	imageOftranscription	blob:null/6fc71f28-d8ba-40a7-ab18-178647df544c
MusicalNotation11	typeOfMusicalNotation	Round notation
	imageOftranscription	blob:null/cc8bdfd0-8573-4dea-a877-40f7e48a0b31
	nextTranscription	MusicalNotation12
MusicalNotation12	imageOftranscription	blob:null/4ab0ce4d-a42e-4f22-9337-0c19c16e9b07
	nextTranscription	MusicalNotation13
MusicalNotation13	imageOftranscription	blob:null/ffcc08f8-e25e-4b37-be9f-f2c293cd6e78
	nextTranscription	MusicalNotation14
MusicalNotation14	imageOftranscription	blob:null/f9ff40bc-8422-4835-bdf4-9bfd991547c8
	nextTranscription	MusicalNotation15
MusicalNotation15	imageOftranscription	blob:null/7ac0cb0f-45ab-400b-bf44-c37e6e4743a4

Table 2.15: Location

Instance	Properties	Range
Location1	url	http://csm.mml.ox.ac.uk/index.php?p=poemdata_view&rec=3
Location2	workNumber	3
	refersAsPart	BibliographicSource1

Table 2.16: BibliographicSource

Instance	Properties	Range
BibliographicSource1	title	Afonso X, o Sábio: Cantigas de Santa Maria
	pubPlace	Madrid
	publisher	Castalia
	numberOfVolumes	3
	date	1959–1972
	hasCreator	Creator1

Table 2.17: StanzaPattern

Instance	Properties	Range
SP1	syllabicMetricalScheme	7' 7 7' 7

Table 2.18: WorkPattern

Instance	Properties	Range
WorkPattern1	syllabicMetricalScheme	7 7 7 7 7 7 7
	rhymeScheme	ABAB/cdcdcdcB
	numberOfStanzas	5

Chapter 3

Eesti regilaulude andmebaas (I)

Resource: URL

Creator: Patrícia Garrido Teixeira

Editor: Mariana Curado Malta

Table 3.1: Opus

Instance	Properties	Range
Opus1	isRealisedThrough	Redaction1
	isRealisedThrough	Redaction2
	title	Eks tulnud sügisel

Table 3.2: Redaction

Instance	Properties	Range
Redaction1	considers	Witness1
	hasFirstLine	Line1
	date	1921
	genre	Kalendrilaulud
	genre	Laulud noorrahva elust
	title	Eks tulnud sügisel + Oleks see mees minu!
Redaction2	considers	Witness2
	hasFirstLine	Line34
	date	1893
	genre	Kalendrilaulud
	title	Eks tulnud sügisel

Table 3.3: Line

Instance	Properties	Range
Line1	nextLine	Line2
	content	Eks ju tulnud sügise,
Line2	nextLine	Line3
	content	Mis sa kehval kevadel.
Line3	nextLine	Line4
	content	Nisud alles niitmata.

Continued on next page

Table 3.3 – continued from previous page

Instance	Properties	Range
Line4	nextLine	Line5
	content	Jaaniks oleks õlut tehtud.
Line5	nextLine	Line6
	content	Erned lesta lepitavad,
	nextPageNumber	77
Line6	nextLine	Line7
	content	Oad kauni kasvatavad
Line7	nextLine	Line8
	content	Oleks see peiu meie käes
Line8	nextLine	Line9
	content	Mis seal sõidab teeda mööda.
Line9	nextLine	Line10
	content	Hobu tal all kui see ahi
Line10	nextLine	Line11
	content	Ise peal kui see päeva
Line11	nextLine	Line12
	content	Oleks see peiu meie käes,
Line12	nextLine	Line13
	content	Sui ma sõidaks saaniga
Line13	nextLine	Line14
	content	Talvel tamme ratastega
Line14	nextLine	Line15
	content	Kevade sea künaga
Line15	nextLine	Line16
	content	Rõgu1 neiukesed vahtsid,
Line16	nextLine	Line17
	content	Pistsid silmad läbi pilu
Line17	nextLine	Line18
	content	Ajasid hambad läbi akna.
Line18	nextLine	Line19
	content	Oleks see peiu meie kaes
Line19	nextLine	Line20
	content	Mis seal sõidab teeda mööda
Line20	nextLine	Line21
	content	Hobu all kui see ahi
Line21	nextLine	Line22
	content	Ise peal ta kui see päeva
	nextPageNumber	78
Line22	nextLine	Line23
	content	Rõngu sild see rõksatas
Line23	nextLine	Line24
	content	Alus palk see praksatas.
Line24	nextLine	Line25
	content	Kas olid äiad, ämmad terved?
Line25	nextLine	Line26
	content	Kas oli pruut kodu jäänud
Line26	nextLine	Line27
	content	Pruut oli kodu surma voodis
Line27	nextLine	Line28
	content	Äiad, ämmad hästi terved.
Line28	nextLine	Line29
	content	Siis mu süda külmaks löödi
Line29	nextLine	Line30
	content	Kui see külm küünla kuu,
Line30	nextLine	Line31
	content	Kui see vali vastla kuu,

Continued on next page

Table 3.3 – continued from previous page

Instance	Properties	Range
Line31	nextLine	Line32
	content	Kui see palav paastu kuu
Line32	nextLine	Line33
	content	Kui see hundi joosu kuu
Line33	content	Kui see saksa kosja kuu.
Line34	nextLine	Line35
	content	Jaaniku poisiku, mes sa tullid kevadelle
Line35	nextLine	Line36
	content	"- "- kevadelt om kehva aiga
Line36	nextLine	Line37
	content	"- "- tule suurel sügiselle
Line37	nextLine	Line38
	content	"- "- sügiselt om suure söögi
Line38	nextLine	Line39
	content	"- "- Suure söögi, suure joogi
Line39	nextLine	Line40
	content	"- "- sügiselt om sia söönü
Line40	nextLine	Line41
	content	"- "- uba ukkert pajo nōa
Line41	nextLine	Line42
	content	"- "- erne äitsep ähna kirja
Line42	nextLine	Line43
	content	"- "- kesi keerutab mäela
Line43	nextLine	Line44
	content	"- "- vesi laulap laeneella
Line44	nextLine	Line45
	content	"- "- umal uigasse oruna
Line45	nextLine	Line46
	content	"- "- kunas me kolmi kokku saame?
Line46	nextLine	Line47
	content	"- "- kolmi kokku kukkumaie
Line47	nextLine	Line48
	content	"- "- all*1 me mehe mürame
Line48	nextLine	Line49
	content	"- "- naise tantsiva tanuta
Line49	content	"- "- latse palla põrmandulla.

Table 3.4: Witness

Instance	Properties	Range
Witness1	hasRole	Role1
	isPart	PrimarySource1
	locus	pages 76-78
Witness2	hasRole	Role1
	isPart	PrimarySource2

Table 3.5: PrimarySource

Instance	Properties	Range
PrimarySource1	belongsTo	Repository1
	siglum	E, StK 7, 76/8 (11)
PrimarySource2	belongsTo	Repository2
	siglum	H II 44, 594 (4)

Table 3.6: Role

Instance	Properties	Range
Role1	function	collector
	isAssignedTo	Person1
	isAssignedTo	Person2

Table 3.7: Person

Instance	Properties	Range
Person1	name	August Ammon, stud.
Person2	name	K. Parts

Table 3.8: Repository

Instance	Properties	Range
Repository1	name	Jaani laul
	isLocatedIn	Place1
Repository2	name	Jaaniku laul
	isLocatedIn	Place2

Table 3.9: Place

Instance	Properties	Range
Place1	settlement	Häädemeeste khk.
Place2	settlement	Otepää khk.

Chapter 4

Eesti regilaulude andmebaas (II)

Resource: URL

Creator: Patrícia Garrido Teixeira

Editor: Mariana Curado Malta

Table 4.1: Opus

Instance	Properties	Range
Opus1	isRealisedThrough	Redaction1
	date	1932
	title	Kadri laul

Table 4.2: Redaction

Instance	Properties	Range
Redaction1	considers	Witness1
	hasFirstLine	Line1
	date	1932
	typeOfRedaction	critical edition

Table 4.3: Line

Instance	Properties	Range
Line1	nextLine	Line2
	content	Emakene, memmekene,
Line2	nextLine	Line3
	content	Pane see tütar mehele,
Line3	nextLine	Line4
	content	Mis käib müüda õuesid,
Line4	nextLine	Line5
	content	Udupea ja udujuuksed,
Line5	nextLine	Line6
	content	Kenad käiksed tal käessa!
	nextPageNumber	10
Line6	nextLine	Line7
	content	Kui ei pane, ei palugi -

Continued on next page

Table 4.3 – continued from previous page

Instance	Properties	Range
Line7	nextLine	Line8
	content	Jäägu koeo kopitsema,
Line8	nextLine	Line9
	content	Aea ääre allitama,
Line9	nextLine	Line10
	content	Seena ääre seenetama.
Line10	nextLine	Line11
	content	Kask tal kasku kaela peale
Line11	nextLine	Line12
	content	Niinepuu nisade peale,
Line12	nextLine	Line13
	content	Kuusik silmakulmu peale,
Line13	content	Kadakas karvade vahele.

Table 4.4: Witness

Instance	Properties	Range
Witness1	hasRole	Role1
	isPart	PrimarySource1
	locus	pages 9-10

Table 4.5: PrimarySource

Instance	Properties	Range
PrimarySource1	belongsTo	Repository1
	comesFrom	Place1
	siglum	AES, MT 93

Table 4.6: Role

Instance	Properties	Range
Role1	function	collector
	isAssignedTo	Person1

Table 4.7: Person

Instance	Properties	Range
Person1	name	P.Palmeos

Table 4.8: Repository

Instance	Properties	Range
Repository1	name	Juuru khk

Table 4.9: Place

Instance	Properties	Range
Place1	settlement	Kaiu v.
	region	Toomja k.

Chapter 5

Eesti regilaulude andmebaas (III)

Resource: URL

Creator: Patrícia Garrido Teixeira

Editor: Mariana Curado Malta

Table 5.1: Opus

Instance	Properties	Range
Opus1	isRealisedThrough	Redaction1
	date	1932
	title	Kadri laul

Table 5.2: Redaction

Instance	Properties	Range
Redaction1	considers	Witness1
	hasFirstLine	Line1
	date	1932
	typeOfRedaction	critical edition

Table 5.3: Line

Instance	Properties	Range
Line1	nextLine	Line2
	content	Emakene, memmekene,
Line2	nextLine	Line3
	content	Pane see tütar mehele,
Line3	nextLine	Line4
	content	Mis käib müüda õuesid,
Line4	nextLine	Line5
	content	Udupea ja udujuuksed,
Line5	nextLine	Line6
	content	Kenad käiksed tal käessa!
	nextPageNumber	10
Line6	nextLine	Line7
	content	Kui ei pane, ei palugi -

Continued on next page

Table 5.3 – continued from previous page

Instance	Properties	Range
Line7	nextLine	Line8
	content	Jäägu koeo kopitsema,
Line8	nextLine	Line9
	content	Aea ääre allitama,
Line9	nextLine	Line10
	content	Seena ääre seenetama.
Line10	nextLine	Line11
	content	Kask tal kasku kaela peale
Line11	nextLine	Line12
	content	Niinepuu nisade peale,
Line12	content	Kuusik silmakulmu peale,
Line13	nextLine	Line13
	content	Kadakas karvade vahele.

Table 5.4: Witness

Instance	Properties	Range
Witness1	hasRole	Role1
	isPart	PrimarySource1
	locus	pages 9-10

Table 5.5: PrimarySource

Instance	Properties	Range
PrimarySource1	belongsTo	Repository1
	comesFrom	Place1
	siglum	AES, MT 93

Table 5.6: Role

Instance	Properties	Range
Role1	function	collector
	isAssignedTo	Person1

Table 5.7: Person

Instance	Properties	Range
Person1	name	P.Palmeos

Table 5.8: Repository

Instance	Properties	Range
Repository1	name	Juuru khk

Table 5.9: Place

Instance	Properties	Range
Place1	settlement	Kaiu v.
	region	Toomja k.

Chapter 6

Eesti regilaulude andmebaas (IV)

Resource: URL

Creator: Patrícia Garrido Teixeira

Editor: Mariana Curado Malta

Table 6.1: Opus

Instance	Properties	Range
Opus1	isRealisedThrough	Redaction1
	date	1932
	title	Kadri laul

Table 6.2: Redaction

Instance	Properties	Range
Redaction1	considers	Witness1
	hasFirstLine	Line1
	date	1932
	typeOfRedaction	critical edition

Table 6.3: Line

Instance	Properties	Range
Line1	nextLine	Line2
	content	Emakene, memmekene,
Line2	nextLine	Line3
	content	Pane see tütar mehele,
Line3	nextLine	Line4
	content	Mis käib müüda õuesid,
Line4	nextLine	Line5
	content	Udupea ja udujuuksed,
Line5	nextLine	Line6
	content	Kenad käiksed tal käessa!
	nextPageNumber	10
Line6	nextLine	Line7
	content	Kui ei pane, ei palugi -

Continued on next page

Table 6.3 – continued from previous page

Instance	Properties	Range
Line7	nextLine	Line8
	content	Jäägu koeo kopitsema,
Line8	nextLine	Line9
	content	Aea ääre allitama,
Line9	nextLine	Line10
	content	Seena ääre seenetama.
Line10	nextLine	Line11
	content	Kask tal kasku kaela peale
Line11	nextLine	Line12
	content	Niinepuu nisade peale,
Line12	nextLine	Line13
	content	Kuusik silmakulmu peale,
Line13	content	Kadakas karvade vahele.

Table 6.4: Witness

Instance	Properties	Range
Witness1	hasRole	Role1
	isPart	PrimarySource1
	locus	pages 9-10

Table 6.5: PrimarySource

Instance	Properties	Range
PrimarySource1	belongsTo	Repository1
	comesFrom	Place1
	siglum	AES, MT 93

Table 6.6: Role

Instance	Properties	Range
Role1	function	collector
	isAssignedTo	Person1

Table 6.7: Person

Instance	Properties	Range
Person1	name	P.Palmeos

Table 6.8: Repository

Instance	Properties	Range
Repository1	name	Juuru khk

Table 6.9: Place

Instance	Properties	Range
Place1	settlement	Kaiu v.
	region	Toomja k.

Chapter 7

MedDB Base de datos da Lírca Profana Galego-Portuguesa

Resource: URL

Creator: Patrícia Garrido Teixeira

Editor: Helena Bermúdez-Sabel

Table 7.1: Opus

Instance	Properties	Range
Opus1	hasCreator	Creator1
	isRealisedThrough	Redaction1
	genre	M
	language	gl
	language	pt
	theme	separación dos namorados
	theme	tristeza
	title	Ondas do mar do Vigo

Table 7.2: Redaction

Instance	Properties	Range
Redaction1	considers	Witness1
	considers	Witness2
	considers	Witness3
	hasFirstStanza	Stanza1
	isAnalysedThrough	WorkPattern1
	isEditedIn	Location2
	isEditedIn	Location3
	isEditedIn	Location4
	isEditedIn	Location5
	isEditedIn	Location6
	isEditedIn	Location7
	isEditedIn	Location8
	isEditedIn	Location9
	isEditedIn	Location10
	isEditedIn	Location11
isEditedIn	Location12	
isEditedIn	Location13	

Continued on next page

Table 7.2 – continued from previous page

Instance	Properties	Range
	isEditedIn	Location14
	isEditedIn	Location14
	isEditedIn	Location15
	isEditedIn	Location16
	isEditedIn	Location17
	isEditedIn	Location18
	isEditedIn	Location19
	isEditedIn	Location20
	isEditedIn	Location21
	isEditedIn	Location22
	isEditedIn	Location23
	isEditedIn	Location24
	retrievesText	Location1
	incipit	Ondas do mar do Vigo
	typeOfRedaction	critical edition

Table 7.3: Stanza

Instance	Properties	Range
Stanza1	hasFirstLine	Line1
	nextStanza	Stanza2
	isAnalysedThrough	StanzaPattern1
	stanzaNumber	1
Stanza2	hasFirstLine	Line4
	nextStanza	Stanza3
	isAnalysedThrough	StanzaPattern2
	stanzaNumber	2
Stanza3	hasFirstLine	Line7
	nextStanza	Stanza4
	isAnalysedThrough	StanzaPattern3
	stanzaNumber	3
Stanza4	hasFirstLine	Line10
	isAnalysedThrough	StanzaPattern4
	stanzaNumber	4

Table 7.4: Line

Instance	Properties	Range
Line1	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern1
	presents	Rhyme1
	nextLine	Line2
	content	Ondas do mar de Vigo,
	isRefrain	false
	lineNumber	1
Line2	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern2
	presents	Rhyme2
	nextLine	Line3
	content	se vistas meu amigo
	isRefrain	false
	lineNumber	2

Continued on next page

Table 7.4 – continued from previous page

Instance	Properties	Range
Line3	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern3
	presents	Rhyme3
	content	e, ai Deus, se verra cedo!
	isRefrain	true
	lineNumber	3
Line4	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern4
	presents	Rhyme4
	nextLine	Line5
	content	Ondas do mar levado,
	isRefrain	false
Line5	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern5
	presents	Rhyme5
	nextLine	Line6
	content	se vistes meu amado,
	isRefrain	false
Line6	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern6
	presents	Rhyme6
	content	e, ai Deus, se verra cedo!
	isRefrain	true
	lineNumber	6
Line7	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern7
	presents	Rhyme7
	nextLine	Line8
	content	Se vistes meu amigo,
	isRefrain	false
Line8	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern8
	presents	Rhyme8
	nextLine	Line9
	content	o por que eu sospiro,
	isRefrain	false
Line9	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern9
	presents	Rhyme9
	nextLine	Line2
	content	e, ai Deus, se verra cedo!
	isRefrain	true
Line10	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern10
	presents	Rhyme10
	nextLine	Line11
	content	Se vistes meu amado,
	isRefrain	false
Line11	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern11
	presents	Rhyme11
	nextLine	Line12
	content	o por que ei gran cuidado,
	isRefrain	false
Line12	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern12
	presents	Rhyme12
	content	e, ai Deus, se verra cedo!
	isRefrain	true
	lineNumber	12

Table 7.5: LinePattern

Instance	Properties	Range
LinePattern1	numberOfSyllables	6
LinePattern2	numberOfSyllables	6
LinePattern3	numberOfSyllables	7
LinePattern4	numberOfSyllables	6
LinePattern5	numberOfSyllables	6
LinePattern6	numberOfSyllables	7
LinePattern7	numberOfSyllables	6
LinePattern8	numberOfSyllables	6
LinePattern9	numberOfSyllables	7
LinePattern10	numberOfSyllables	6
LinePattern11	numberOfSyllables	6
LinePattern12	numberOfSyllables	7

Table 7.6: Location

Instance	Properties	Range
Location1	refersAsPart	BibliographicSource1
	identifier	Codax, 1
Location2	refersAsPart	BibliographicSource3
	identifier	Codax, 1
Location3	refersAsPart	BibliographicSource4
	identifier	Ovidio y Arce 1
Location4	refersAsPart	BibliographicSource5
	identifier	Nunes, Martim Codax, 1
Location5	refersAsPart	BibliographicSource6
	identifier	Bell, Martim Codax, 1
Location6	refersAsPart	BibliographicSource7
	identifier	Amigo 491
Location7	refersAsPart	BibliographicSource8
	identifier	Auswahl
Location8	refersAsPart	BibliographicSource9
	locus	pp.206-207,511-512
Location9	refersAsPart	BibliographicSource10
	identifier	Antoloxía, 142
Location10	refersAsPart	BibliographicSource11
	locus	p. 513
Location11	refersAsPart	BibliographicSource2
	identifier	Machado 1227
Location12	refersAsPart	BibliographicSource12
	identifier	Braga 884
Location13	refersAsPart	BibliographicSource13
	locus	pp.259-260
Location14	refersAsPart	BibliographicSource14
	locus	p.95
Location15	refersAsPart	BibliographicSource15
	identifier	Cinquenta cant., 27
Location16	refersAsPart	BibliographicSource16
	identifier	O cervo, 37
Location17	refersAsPart	BibliographicSource17
	locus	p.4

Continued on next page

Table 7.6 – continued from previous page

Instance	Properties	Range
Location18	refersAsPart	BibliographicSource18
	locus	p. 101
Location19	refersAsPart	BibliographicSource19
	locus	p.76
Location20	refersAsPart	BibliographicSource20
	locus	pp.56-57
Location21	refersAsPart	BibliographicSource21b
	identifier	67
Location22	refersAsPart	BibliographicSource22
	identifier	Manual, 11
Location23	refersAsPart	BibliographicSource23
	identifier	Literatura, 2
Location24	refersAsPart	BibliographicSource24
	identifier	Piccolo 111
Location25	identifier	26:124
Location26	identifier	26:124
Location27	identifier	26:124
Location28	identifier	26:124

Table 7.7: BibliographicSource

Instance	Properties	Range
BibliographicSource1	hasCreator	Creator2
	date	1998
	pubPlace	Santiago de Compostela
	publisher	Xunta de Galicia
	title	Cantigas do Mar de Vigo
	typeOfEdition	crítica
BibliographicSource2	hasCreator	Creator3
	date	1949-1964
	numberOfVolumes	8
	pubPlace	Lisboa
	publisher	Edição da Revista de Portugal
	title	Cancioneiro da Biblioteca Nacional
	typeOfEdition	paleográfica
BibliographicSource3	hasCreator	Creator4
	date	1956
	pubPlace	Rio de Janeiro
	publisher	Departamento de Imprensa Nacional
	title	O cancionero de Martim Codax
	typeOfEdition	crítica
BibliographicSource4	hasCreator	Creator5
	date	1916
	publisher	Boletín de la Real Academia Gallega
	title	El genuino Martin Codax
	typeOfEdition	crítica
	issueNumber	13
	scope	121-135
BibliographicSource5	hasCreator	Creator6
	date	1931
	publisher	Revista Lusitana
	title	Cantigas de Martim Codax, presumido joglar do século XIII

Continued on next page

Table 7.7 – continued from previous page

Instance	Properties	Range
	typeOfEdition	crítica
	issueNumber	29
	scope	5-32
BibliographicSource6	hasCreator	Creator7
	date	1923
	publisher	The Modern Language Review
	title	The Seven Songs of Martin Codax
	typeOfEdition	crítica
	issueNumber	18
	scope	162-167
BibliographicSource7	hasCreator	Creator8
	date	1973
	publisher	Centro do Livro Brasileiro
	title	Cantigas d'Amigo dos trovadores galego-portugueses
	typeOfEdition	crítica
	numberOfVolumes	3
	pubPlace	Lisboa
BibliographicSource8	hasCreator	Creator9
	date	1928
	publisher	Max Niemeyer
	title	Auswahl Altportugiesischer Lieder
	typeOfEdition	crítica
	pubPlace	Halle
BibliographicSource9	hasCreator	Creator10
	date	1992
	publisher	Garlans Publishing, Inc.
	title	Medieval Galician-Portuguese Poetry. An Anthology
	typeOfEdition	crítica
	pubPlace	New York-London
BibliographicSource10	hasCreator	Creator11
	date	2003
	publisher	Xerais
	title	Antoloxía da lírica galego-portuguesa
	typeOfEdition	crítica
	pubPlace	Vigo
BibliographicSource11	hasCreator	Creator12
	date	2003
	publisher	Campo das letras
	title	500 cantigas de amigo
	typeOfEdition	crítica
	pubPlace	Porto
BibliographicSource12	hasCreator	Creator13
	date	1878
	publisher	Imprensa Nacional
	title	Cancioneiro Portuguez da Vaticana.
	title	Edição crítica restituída sobre o texto diplomático de Halle, acompanhada de um glossário e de uma introdução sobre os trovadores e cancioneros portugueses
	typeOfEdition	paleográfica
	pubPlace	Lisboa

Continued on next page

Table 7.7 – continued from previous page

Instance	Properties	Range
BibliographicSource13	hasCreator	Creator14
	date	1906
	publisher	Livraria Clássica Editora
	title	Crestomatia Arcaica.
	subtitle	Crestomatia Arcaica. Excertos da Literatura Portuguesa desde o que mais antigo se conhece até o século XVI, acompanhados de introdução gramatical, notas e glossário
	typeOfEdition	divulgativa
BibliographicSource14	pubPlace	Lisboa
	hasCreator	Creator15
	date	1959
	title	Textos portugueses medievais
	typeOfEdition	divulgativa
BibliographicSource15	pubPlace	Coimbra
	hasCreator	Creator16
	isPart	BibliographicSource15b
	title	Cinquenta cantigas de amigo
	typeOfEdition	divulgativa
	scope	71-250
BibliographicSource15b	sectionNumber	4
	date	1976
	publisher	Assirio e Alvin
	pubPlace	Lisboa
BibliographicSource16	title	Do cancionero de amigo
	hasCreator	Creator17
	isPart	BibliographicSource16b
	title	O cervo do monte a auga volvia
BibliographicSource16b	typeOfEdition	divulgativa
	date	1984
	pubPlace	Ferrol
	title	Del simbolismo naturalista en la cantiga de amigo
BibliographicSource17	publisher	Esquio
	hasCreator	Creator18
	date	1977
	publisher	Seara Novo
	title	Poesia medieval. I. Cantigas de amigo
	typeOfEdition	divulgativa
BibliographicSource18	pubPlace	Lisboa
	editionNumber	5
	hasCreator	Creator19
	date	1991
	publisher	Editora Ulisseia
	title	Antologia Literaria Comentada. Idade Média. Fernão Lopes
	typeOfEdition	divulgativa
BibliographicSource19	pubPlace	Lisboa
	editionNumber	5
	hasCreator	Creator20
	date	1988
	publisher	Editora Ulisseia
	title	Poesia e prosa medievais
BibliographicSource19	typeOfEdition	divulgativa
	pubPlace	Lisboa
	editionNumber	2
	title	Poesia e prosa medievais

Continued on next page

Table 7.7 – continued from previous page

Instance	Properties	Range
BibliographicSource20	hasCreator	Creator21
	date	1961
	publisher	Livraria Sá da Costa Editora
	title	Antologia de textos medievais
	typeOfEdition	divulgativa
	pubPlace	Lisboa
BibliographicSource21	hasCreator	Creator22
	date	1990
	publisher	Sotelo Blanco
	title	Literatura Galega Medieval
	pubPlace	Santiago de Compostela
	editionNumber	2
BibliographicSource21b	isPart	BibliographicSource21
	date	1990
	typeOfEdition	divulgativa
	title	Antoloxía de textos comentados (lírica e prosa)
	volumeNumber	2
BibliographicSource22	hasCreator	Creator23
	date	1993
	publisher	Sotelo Blanco
	title	Manual e antoloxía da Literatura Galega Medieval
	typeOfEdition	divulgativa
	pubPlace	Santiago de Compostela
BibliographicSource23	hasCreator	Creator24
	date	1987
	publisher	Vía Láctea
	title	Literatura Galego-Portuguesa Medieval
	typeOfEdition	divulgativa
	pubPlace	A Coruña
BibliographicSource24	hasCreator	Creator25
	date	1951
	publisher	Edizioni scientifiche Italiane
	title	Antologia della lirica d'amore gallego-portoghese
	typeOfEdition	divulgativa
	pubPlace	Napoli

Table 7.8: Creator

Instance	Properties	Range
Creator1	isA	Person1
Creator2	isA	Person2
Creator3	isA	Person3
	isA	Person4
Creator4	isA	Person5
Creator5	isA	Person6
Creator6	isA	Person7
Creator7	isA	Person8
Creator8	isA	Person9
Creator9	isA	Person10
Creator10	isA	Person11

Continued on next page

Table 7.8 – continued from previous page

Instance	Properties	Range
Creator11	isA	Person12
Creator12	isA	Person13
Creator13	isA	Person14
Creator14	isA	Person15
Creator15	isA	Person16
	isA	Person17
Creator16	isA	Person18
	isA	Person19
Creator17	isA	Person19
	isA	Person20
Creator18	isA	Person21
Creator19	isA	Person22
Creator20	isA	Person23
Creator21	isA	Person24
Creator22	isA	Person25
Creator23	isA	Person26
Creator24	isA	Person27
	isA	Person28
	isA	Person29
	isA	Person30
Creator25	isA	Person31

Table 7.9: Person

Instance	Properties	Range
Person1	nationality	Galega
	altName	MartCod
	biography	Xograr galego do que a tradición manuscrita trasmitiu sete cantigas de amigo. A súa colocación no hipotético Cancioneiro de Xograres Galegos fai pensar nunha actividade focalizada arredor do período 1240 - 1280. Ata o momento, as fontes documentais sacadas á luz non achegaron datos seguros sobre o autor. Moito se ten especulado sobre o seu nome, non só sobre o étimo e significado, senón mesmo sobre a súa correcta pronunciación, que pode ser grave ou aguda. Codax é a forma maioritaria nos testemuños manuscritos, pero cómpre non esquecer que o nome, nunha nota que figura en V882, aparece grafado Codaz, polo que as teses en cuestión deberían considerar tamén esta forma gráfica. O silencio documental fai que as conxecturas se centren no topónimo Vigo, presente nas súas cantigas, identificando o santuario coa igrexa de Santiago de Vigo. Non se deben desbotar, con todo, outras posibles localizacións, como a ermida de Santa Uxía, doada por Fernando II de León en 1160 ao mosteiro de Melón e que quedaba fóra das murallas da vila, á beira do mar, no barrio do Berbés. A actividade poético-musical do xograr tampouco é doada de establecer, aínda que case todos os estudosos privilexian, en función do contido da cantiga B1279/V885 (N2), a presenza de Martín Codax na Reconquista de Andalucía, na que participaría no séquito dalgún magnate en tempos de Fernando III. Gutiérrez García (2014: 122) refire a presenza, na documentación do Tumbo primeiro (séc. X) de Sobrado dos Monxes, da localidade Codais (variantes Codays, Quodais e Quodaix) na terra de Nendos, identificada con Santo Estevo de Cos, parroquia do actual concello de Abegondo, o que abriría a posibilidade de que o apelido tivese a súa orixe na toponimia setentrional galega. Ron Fernández (2014: 122), pola súa banda, encontra un Martin Codeas, que mora no lugar de Gogim, freguesía de Sabadim, nunha sentenza de 1290 do rei Don Denis, e un Fernan Codaz na documentación do mosteiro de Oia, onde Fernan aparece como dono dunha chousa que lle pertenceu en Sandián, localidade situada no concello pontevedrés de O Rosal (Oia, carp. 1084, doc.19 1275-nov.-11; carp.1806, doc. 11, 1278-out.-5).
	birthPlaceCertainty	Probábel
	floruitFrom	1240
	floruitTo	1280
	name	Martin Codax
	socialStatus	indeterminada
	literaryPeriod	1240-1300
	Person2	name
Person3	name	Elsa Paxeco Machado
Person4	name	José Pedro Machado
Person5	name	Celso Ferreira da Cunha
Person6	name	Eladio Ovidio y Arce
Person7	name	José Joaquim Nunes
Person8	name	F.G. Aubrey Bell
Person9	name	José Joaquim Nunes
Person10	name	Silvio Pellegrini
Person11	name	Frede Jensen
Person12	name	Xosé Bieito Arias Freixedo
Person13	name	Rip Cohen

Continued on next page

Table 7.9 – continued from previous page

Instance	Properties	Range
Person14	name	Teófilo Braga
Person15	name	Manuel Rodrigues Lapa
Person16	name	Correa de Oliveira
Person17	name	E. Saavedra Machado
Person18	name	Stephen Reckert
Person19	name	Helder Macedo
Person20	name	Vicenç Beltran
Person21	name	Hernani Cidade
Person22	name	M Ema Tarracha Ferreira
Person23	name	M Ema Tarracha Ferreira
Person24	name	José Pereira Tavares
Person25	name	Xosé Ramón Pena
Person26	name	Xosé Ramon Pena
Person27	name	Xosé María Dobarro Paz
Person28	name	Xosé Ramón Fraxeiro Mato
Person29	name	Carlos Paulo Martínez Pereiro
Person30	name	Francisco Salinas Portugal
Person31	name	Francesco Piccolo

Table 7.10: Rhyme

Instance	Properties	Range
Rhyme1	ending	igo
	rhymeWord	Vigo
Rhyme2	ending	igo
	rhymeWord	amigo
Rhyme3	ending	edo
	rhymeWord	cedo
Rhyme4	ending	ado
	rhymeWord	levado
Rhyme5	ending	ado
	rhymeWord	amado
Rhyme6	ending	edo
	rhymeWord	cedo
Rhyme7	ending	igo
	rhymeWord	amigo
Rhyme8	ending	iro
	rhymeWord	sospiro
Rhyme9	ending	edo
	rhymeWord	cedo
Rhyme10	ending	ado
	rhymeWord	amado
Rhyme11	ending	ado
	rhymeWord	coidado
Rhyme12	ending	edo
	rhymeWord	cedo

Table 7.11: StanzaPattern

Instance	Properties	Range
StanzaPattern1	isReferencedIn	Location25
	metricalType	Estrofa
	numberOfLines	2+1
	rhymeScheme	aaB
	syllabicMetricalScheme	6'6'7'
StanzaPattern2	isReferencedIn	Location26
	metricalType	estrofa
	numberOfLines	2+1
	rhymeScheme	aaB
	syllabicMetricalScheme	6'6'7'
StanzaPattern3	isReferencedIn	Location27
	metricalType	Estrofa
	numberOfLines	2+1
	rhymeScheme	aaB
	syllabicMetricalScheme	6'6'7'
StanzaPattern4	isReferencedIn	Location28
	metricalType	Estrofa
	numberOfLines	2+1
	rhymeScheme	aaB
	syllabicMetricalScheme	6'6'7'

Table 7.12: Witness

Instance	Properties	Range
Witness1	hasItem	Paratext1
	isReproducedIn	Facsimile1
	hasMusicalNotation	false
	hasMusicSpace	false
	locus	269r-269v
	siglum	B
	workNumber	1278
Witness2	isReproducedIn	Facsimile3
	hasMusicalNotation	true
	hasMusicSpace	false
	locus	1r
	siglum	N
	workNumber	1
Witness3	isReproducedIn	Facsimile4
	hasMusicalNotation	false
	hasMusicSpace	false
	locus	139v
	siglum	V
	workNumber	1

Table 7.13: Facsimile

Instance	Properties	Range
Facsimile1	nextPage	Facsimile2
	url	https://www.cirp.gal/pls/bdo2/f?p=129:20:433767334949176793:::P20_IDM:0493

Continued on next page

Table 7.13 – continued from previous page

Instance	Properties	Range
Facsimile2	url	https://www.cirp.gal/pls/bdo2/f?p=129:20:433767334949176793 :::P20_IDM:0494
Facsimile3	url	https://www.cirp.gal/pls/bdo2/f?p=129:20:433767334949176793 :::P20_IDM:0494
Facsimile4	url	https://www.cirp.gal/pls/bdo2/f?p=129:20:433767334949176793 :::P20_IDM:0886

Table 7.14: Paratext

Instance	Properties	Range
Paratext1	typeOfParatext	Nota colocciana
	originalContent	tornel
	notes	Nota colocciana que precede a cantiga B 1278. Está situada na col. b do fol 269r.

Table 7.15: WorkPattern

Instance	Properties	Range
WorkPattern1	numberOfStanzas	4
	interstrophicRelations	Cobras alternas
	hasRefrain	true

Chapter 8

Russian Poetry (Birnbaum—Thorsen)

Resource: URL

Creator: Helena Bermúdez-Sabel

Notes: Important: the contents of each line are expressed as the data property content.Line. However, it would have been more accurate to divide the line in syllables so as to use the property: isStressed.Syllable in order to retrieve the stressed vowels (as in the source). Ignorance of syllable structure in Russian make it impossible for the encoder to model the contents that way.

Table 8.1: Opus

Instance	Properties	Range
Opus1	title	Нелюбовь
	hasCreator	Creator1
	isRealisedThrough	Redaction1

Table 8.2: Creator

Instance	Properties	Range
Creator1	isA	Person1

Table 8.3: Person

Instance	Properties	Range
Person1	name	Зинаида Николаевна Гишпиус
Person2	name	В. Венгеровой

Table 8.4: Redaction

Instance	Properties	Range
Redaction1	hasFirstStanza	Stanza1
	isDedicatedTo	Person2

Table 8.5: Stanza

Instance	Properties	Range
Stanza1	hasFirstLine	Line1
	nextStanza	Stanza2
Stanza2	hasFirstLine	Line5
	nextStanza	Stanza3
Stanza3	hasFirstLine	Line9
	nextStanza	Stanza4
Stanza4	hasFirstLine	Line13

Table 8.6: Line

Instance	Properties	Range
Line1	lineNumber	1
	content	Как ветер мокрый, ты бьёшься в ставни,
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern1
	nextLine	Line2
	presents	RhymeA
Line2	lineNumber	2
	content	Как ветер чёрный, поёшь: ты мой!
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern2
	nextLine	Line3
	presents	RhymeB
Line3	lineNumber	3
	content	Как ветер чёрный, поёшь: ты мой!
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern3
	nextLine	Line4
	presents	RhymeA
Line4	lineNumber	4
	content	Твой друг единый,— открой, открой!
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern4
	presents	RhymeB
Line5	lineNumber	5
	content	Держу я ставни, открыть не смею,
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern5
	nextLine	Line6
	presents	RhymeA
Line6	lineNumber	6
	content	Держусь за ставни и страх таю.
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern6
	nextLine	Line7
	presents	RhymeB
Line7	lineNumber	7
	content	Храню, лелею, храню, жалею
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern7
	nextLine	Line8
	presents	RhymeA
Line8	lineNumber	8
	content	Мой луч последний— любовь мою.
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern8
	presents	RhymeB
	lineNumber	9

Continued on next page

Line9

Table 8.6 – continued from previous page

Instance	Properties	Range
	content	Смеется хаос, зовет безокий:
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern9
	nextLine	Line10
	presents	RhymeA
Line10	lineNumber	10
	content	Умрешь в оковах,— порви, порви!
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern10
	nextLine	Line11
Line11	presents	RhymeB
	lineNumber	11
	content	Ты знаешь счастье, ты одинокий,
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern11
Line12	nextLine	Line12
	presents	RhymeA
	lineNumber	12
	content	В свободе счастье— и в Нелюбви.
Line13	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern12
	presents	RhymeB
	lineNumber	13
	content	Охладевая, творю молитву,
Line14	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern13
	nextLine	Line14
	presents	RhymeA
	lineNumber	14
Line15	content	Любви молитву едва творю...
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern14
	nextLine	Line15
	presents	RhymeB
Line16	lineNumber	15
	content	Слабеют руки, кончаю битву,
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern15
	nextLine	Line16
Line16	presents	RhymeA
	lineNumber	16
	content	Слабеют руки, кончаю битву,
	isAnalysedThrough	LinePattern16
	presents	RhymeB

Table 8.7: LinePattern

Instance	Properties	Range
LinePattern1	accentedVowels	E O O A
	hasFirstFoot	FootA
LinePattern2	accentedVowels	E O O O
	hasFirstFoot	FootB
LinePattern3	accentedVowels	E A U A
	hasFirstFoot	FootA
LinePattern4	accentedVowels	U I O O
	hasFirstFoot	FootB
LinePattern5	accentedVowels	U A I E
	hasFirstFoot	FootA
LinePattern6	accentedVowels	U A A U
	hasFirstFoot	FootB

Continued on next page

Table 8.7 – continued from previous page

Instance	Properties	Range
LinePattern7	accentedVowels	U E U E
	hasFirstFoot	FootA
LinePattern8	accentedVowels	U E O U
	hasFirstFoot	FootB
LinePattern9	accentedVowels	O A O O
	hasFirstFoot	FootA
LinePattern10	accentedVowels	O O I I
	hasFirstFoot	FootB
LinePattern11	accentedVowels	A A O
	hasFirstFoot	FootC
LinePattern12	accentedVowels	O A I
	hasFirstFoot	FootD
LinePattern13	accentedVowels	A U I
	hasFirstFoot	FootE
LinePattern14	accentedVowels	I I A U
	hasFirstFoot	FootB
LinePattern15	accentedVowels	E U A I
	hasFirstFoot	FootA
LinePattern16	accentedVowels	E U U
	hasFirstFoot	FootF

Table 8.8: Foot

Instance	Properties	Range
FootA	syllabicScheme	ox
	nextFoot	Foot2a
Foot2a	syllabicScheme	ox(o)
	nextFootAfterCaesura	Foot3a
Foot3a	syllabicScheme	ox
	nextFoot	Foot4a
Foot4a	syllabicScheme	ox(o)
FootB	syllabicScheme	ox
	nextFoot	Foot2b
Foot2b	syllabicScheme	ox(o)
	nextFootAfterCaesura	Foot3b
Foot3b	syllabicScheme	ox
	nextFoot	Foot4b
Foot4b	syllabicScheme	ox
FootC	syllabicScheme	ox
	nextFoot	Foot2c
Foot2c	syllabicScheme	ox(o)
	nextFootAfterCaesura	Foot3c
Foot3c	syllabicScheme	oo
	isIrregular	true
	nextFoot	Foot4c
Foot4c	syllabicScheme	ox(o)
FootD	syllabicScheme	ox
	nextFoot	Foot2d
Foot2d	syllabicScheme	ox(o)
	nextFootAfterCaesura	Foot3d
Foot3d	syllabicScheme	oo
	isIrregular	true
	nextFoot	Foot4d

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Table 8.8 – continued from previous page

Instance	Properties	Range
Foot4d	syllabicScheme	ox
FootE	syllabicScheme	ox
	nextFoot	Foot2e
Foot2e	syllabicScheme	oo(o)
	isIrregular	true
	nextFootAfterCaesura	Foot3e
Foot3e	syllabicScheme	ox
	nextFoot	Foot4e
Foot4e	syllabicScheme	ox
FootF	syllabicScheme	ox
	nextFoot	Foot2f
Foot2f	syllabicScheme	ox(o)
	nextFootAfterCaesura	Foot3f
Foot3f	syllabicScheme	oo
	isIrregular	true
	nextFoot	Foot4f
Foot4f	syllabicScheme	ox

Table 8.9: Rhyme

Instance	Properties	Range
RhymeA	label	A
RhymeB	label	b

Chapter 9

Skaldic Project

Resource: URL

Creators: Patrícia Garrido Teixeira & Mariana Curado Malta

Editor: Mariana Curado Malta

Table 9.1: Opus

Instance	Properties	Range
Opus1	literaryPeriod	Viking Period
	isRealisedThrough	Redaction1

Table 9.2: Redaction

Instance	Properties	Range
Redaction1	hasEditor	Person1
	typeOfRedaction	scholarly curated
	considers	Witness1
	hasFirstLine	Line1
	isEditedIn	Location1
	isEditedIn	Location2
	isEditedIn	Location3
	isEditedIn	Location4
	isEditedIn	Location5

Table 9.3: Line

Instance	Properties	Range
Line1	content	Pórðr ok Þórunnr
	nextLine	Line2
Line2	content	þenna reistu stein
	nextLine	Line3
Line3	content	eptir Erra,
	nextLine	Line4
Line4	content	algóðan dreng.

Table 9.4: Witness

Instance	Properties	Range
Witness1	siglum	Run Vg 32VI
	isPart	PrimarySource1

Table 9.5: PrimarySource

Instance	Properties	Range
PrimarySource1	comesFrom	Place1

Table 9.6: Place

Instance	Properties	Range
Place1	name	Västergötland

Table 9.7: BibliographicSource

Instance	Properties	Range
BibliographicSource1	title	Runverser
	date	1887-91
	series	Antiqvarisk tidskrift för Sverige
	seriesNumber	10
	pubPlace	Stockholm
	publisher	Ivar Hæggström
	hasCreator	Creator1
BibliographicSource2	title	Västergötlands runinskrifter
	date	1940-70
	series	Sveriges runinskrifter
	seriesNumber	5
	pubPlace	Stockholm
	publisher	Almqvist & Wiksell
	hasEditor	Person3
	hasEditor	Person4
BibliographicSource3	title	Runstenen i Kållands Åsaka
	date	1959
	volumeNumber	74
	scope	227-35
	hasCreator	Creator2
	isPart	BibliographicSource3b
BibliographicSource3b	title	ANF
BibliographicSource4	title	Schwedische Runendichtung der Wikingerzeit
	date	1996
	series	Runrön
	seriesNumber	10
	pubPlace	Uppsala
	publisher	Institutionen för nordiska språk, Uppsala universitet
	hasCreator	Creator3

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Table 9.7 – continued from previous page

Instance	Properties	Range
BibliographicSource5	title	Review of Frank Hübler. 1996. Schwedische Runendichtung der Wikingerzeit. Runrön 10. Uppsala: Institutionen för nordiska språk, Uppsala universitet
	date	1998
	volumeNumber	8
	scope	93-7
	hasCreator	Creator4
	isPart	BibliographicSource5b
BibliographicSource5b	title	ALV

Table 9.8: Location

Instance	Properties	Range
Location1	locus	367-8
	refersAsPart	BibliographicSource1
Location2	locus	49-50
	identifier	Pl. 28
Location3	refersAsPart	BibliographicSource2
	refersAsPart	BibliographicSource3
Location4	locus	45
	refersAsPart	BibliographicSource4
Location5	locus	98
	refersAsPart	BibliographicSource5

Table 9.9: Creator

Instance	Properties	Range
Creator1	isA	Person1
	isA	Person2
Creator2	isA	Person5
Creator3	isA	Person6
Creator4	isA	Person7

Table 9.10: Person

Instance	Properties	Range
Person1	surname	Brate
	forename	Erik
Person2	surname	Bugge
	forename	Sophus
Person3	surname	Jungner
	forename	Hugo
Person4	surname	Svärdström
	forename	Elisabeth
Person5	surname	Salberger

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Table 9.10 – continued from previous page

Instance	Properties	Range
	forename	Evert
Person6	surname	Hübler
	forename	Frank
Person7	surname	Wulf
	forename	Fred